

Complexes of Cadmium(II) iodide with Substituted Pyridine-N-oxides and Their Reaction with Some Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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Cadmium(II) iodide when reacted separately with β -picoline-N-oxide(L) and γ -picoline-N-oxide(L') in ethanolic medium formed two crystalline compounds having the composition CdI_2 and $CdLI_2$. These are apparently three coordinated but are presumably tetrahedral through dimerisation. These dimers were separately reacted with nitrogen donor ligands like quinoline and isoquinoline(L'') in a mixed solvent medium and mixed ligand complexes were characterised by analysis and i.r. spectra.

CADMIUM ion has a completely filled $4d^{10}$ configuration which usually favours tetrahedral form.

But with a judicious selection of the ligands containing heterodonor atoms with varying donor characteristics, the coordination of the cation may be increased. This depends upon the electro-negativities of the ligand donor atoms which determine the extent of charge transfer from the ligand to the metal ion per each sigma bond.

Pyridine N-oxide and its derivatives are known to form¹⁻⁷ a large number of compounds with several transitional and non-transitional metal halides and pseudo halides. The ligands coordinate to the metal through oxygen. They are reported to function as unidentate ligands⁸ and also as bridging ligands⁹. Similarly, the coordinating behaviour of quinoline and isoquinoline is also well studied. In this communication, attempts were made to prepare some cadmium complexes containing both picoline-N-oxide and quinoline or isoquinoline.

Experimental

1. $Cd(3\text{-pic-N-O})I_2$.
2. $Cd(4\text{-pic-N-O})I_2$.

Hot ethanolic solution of cadmium iodide was treated with 3-picoline-N-oxide/4-picoline-N-oxide in 1 : 2 molar ratio and was stirred well when white crystalline substance separated out. It was suction filtered, washed with ethanol, ether and finally dried in *vacuo*.

3. $CdI_2(3\text{-pic-N-O})Q_2$.
4. $CdI_2(4\text{-pic-N-O})Q_2$.
5. $CdI_2(3\text{-pic-N-O})IQ_2$.
6. $CdI_2(4\text{-pic-N-O})IQ_2$.

To a hot solution of $CdI_2(3\text{-pic-N-O}/4\text{-pic-N-O})$ in a mixed solvent of ethanol-acetone (2 : 1 v/v), was added quinoline/isoquinoline in 1 : 4 molar ratio and was refluxed for 2 hours. The resulting clear solution on cooling overnight gave beautiful crystalline compounds which were suction filtered, washed with ether and finally dried in *vacuo*.

Analyses :

The purity of the isolated compound was established in all cases by estimating the metal and the halogen following standard methods. The former was estimated as $CdNH_4PO_4 \cdot H_2O$ and the latter was precipitated as silver halide only after alkaline fusion to avoid the interference of N-oxide¹⁰. All the complexes were soluble in acetone.

Physical Measurements :

Infra-red absorption spectra in the range of 5000-650 cm^{-1} were recorded on Nujol mulls using Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on solid specimens using Guoy method and they were all found to be diamagnetic as expected for Cd(II) ion with completely filled 4d shell. The molar conductance was measured for $\sim 10^{-3}M$ solutions in acetone using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge, type CL 0102 and a dip type cell. The low values obtained are indicative of the non-electrolytic nature of the isolated complexes, the Δ_{∞} values for 1 : 1 electrolytes in acetone being ~ 150 mhos.

The melting points, analyses and the conductance data of the compounds are recorded in Table-1.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, M. P. AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF THE MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF CADMIUM

Compound	Colour and Form.	M. P. (°C)	%Cadmium		%Halogen		Λ_m in acetone (mhos)
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
CdI ₂ (3-pic-N-O)	White crystalline	215	23.2	23.7	53.1	53.4	27
CdI ₂ (4-pic-N-O)	White crystalline	230	23.4	23.7	53.2	53.4	27
CdI ₂ (3-pic-N-O)Q ₂	White crystalline	190	15.5	15.3	34.1	34.6	22
CdI ₂ (4-pic-N-O)Q ₂	Pale yellow crystalline	210	15.1	15.3	34.2	34.6	18
CdI ₂ (3-pic-N-O)IQ ₂	Pale yellow crystalline (Needle-shaped)	180	15.3	15.3	34.2	34.6	31
CdI ₂ (4-pic-N-O)IQ ₂	Pale yellow crystalline (Needle-shaped)	165	13.3	13.1	29.1	29.4	22

Results and Discussion

Pyridine N-oxide and substituted pyridine N-oxides form complexes with varied stoichiometries with dipositive transitional metal halides. In the present investigation it has been observed that even if excess of pic-N-oxide is added to the metal halide, only one molecule of the ligand gets into the resulting complex, CdLI₂. The elemental analysis confirms this composition. These are apparently three coordinated but are presumably four coordinated tetrahedral complexes through dimerisation by halogen bridging. Direct evidence for the presence of halogen bridges from infra-red spectra could not be obtained due to the limited range of the instrument used. The infra-red spectra of the compounds are very informative. The bonding of N-oxide ligands to the metal ion is usually discussed from three fundamental vibrations viz., ν (N-O), δ (N-O) and γ (C-H) of the ligands in the free state and on complexation. It has been reported¹¹⁻¹³ that on complexation, the ν (N-O) undergoes considerable negative shift, δ (N-O), no significant change and γ (C-H) will have either small positive or negative shift or will be at the same position.

The strong absorption bands at ~ 1250 , 855 and 740 cm^{-1} in the i.r. spectra of free pyridine N-oxides (as Nujol mulls) are assigned to the above three fundamental vibrations. The N-O stretching frequency in the complexes under report (Table 2) occurs in the range 1200-1242 cm^{-1} . The shifting of this band from 1250 cm^{-1} in the free ligand to the lower frequency is attributed to a change in the (N-O) bond order as result of oxygen-metal coordination^{12,14}. The (N-O) bending vibration in

all the complexes reported (Table 2) occurs in the range 794-820 cm^{-1} . Hence the δ (N-O) shows a negative shift in all the complexes. This negative shift suggests that the mass effect due to coordinated metal ion on δ (N-O) is outweighing the effect due to coordination¹⁵. The γ (C-H) vibration of the ligand has also undergone either positive or negative shift as observed earlier.

In addition to the above absorption bands due to N-oxides the characteristic band round about 1600 cm^{-1} due to bonded quinoline or isoquinoline is also observed indicating their presence in the mixed ligand complexes.

The stereochemistry of coordination number five and six are very well known. Whilst hexa-coordinated octahedral compounds are more known, penta-coordination is comparatively rare. Penta-coordinated cadmium compounds involve the use of 5s5p³5d hybrid orbitals for bonding. Cadmium terpyridyl chloride was amongst the first few reported penta-coordinated complexes of cadmium(II) and this prefers a trigonal bipyramidal structure. Subsequently several penta-coordinated cadmium(II) complexes have been reported¹⁶. In this communication the compounds having the composition CdI₂.LL'₂ are presumably penta-coordinated. They have low melting points and are monomeric. The molar conductance values are low as compared to ~ 150 mhos for a 1 : 1 electrolyte and these low Λ_m values are presumably due to slight dissociation. Amongst the ligands used, isoquinoline is less basic than quinoline and similarly 4-picoline-N-oxide is less basic than 3-picoline-N-oxide. Hence when isoquinoline and 4-picoline-N-oxide are used together as ligands, the coordination number increases to six as evidenced by the compound, CdI₂(4-pic-N-O)IQ₂.

TABLE 2—SOME FUNDAMENTAL VIBRATIONS (cm^{-1}) OF SUBSTITUTED PYRIDINE N-OXIDE IN MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF CADMIUM(II)

Compound	ν (N-O)	δ (N-O)	γ (C-H)
Cd(3-pic-N-O)I ₂	1242(br)	794(v.s)	730(s)
Cd(4-pic-N-O)I ₂	1200(s)	816(v.s)	746 s)
CdI ₂ (3-pic-N-O)Q ₂	1234(v.s)	800(v.s)	720(s)
CdI ₂ (4-pic-N-O)Q ₂	1206(v.s)	820 v.s)	756 v.s)
CdI ₂ (3-pic-N-O)IQ ₂	1206(s)	810 br)	724(s)
CdI ₂ (4-pic-N-O)IQ ₂	1220(s)	820(s)	736(s)

Q=quinoline and IQ=isoquinoline.
v.s.=very sharp, br=broad, s=sharp.

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